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UZBEK-CHINESE RELATIONS ON THE WAY OF IMPLEMENTING A CONSISTENT, PEACE-LOVING CONSTITUTIONAL POLICY OF THE COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights the prospects for cooperation between Uzbekistan and China, aimed at developing trade, economic and investment relations in the context of constitutional reforms. Priority is given to infrastructure projects to expand new export markets. Guidelines for the development of bilateral relations in the fields of energy, industry, transport, innovation, green and digital economy are presented, as well as experience in diversifying the infrastructure network and expanding new export markets. Attention was focused on the exchange of experience in the field of culture, education, healthcare, tourism, sports and other areas of mutual interest, friendly contacts between the media, scientific and educational institutions, and artistic groups of the two countries.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, China, bilateral cooperation, infrastructure projects, industry, economy, humanitarian ties, “green” and digital economy, diversification, humanitarian ties.

INTRODUCTION

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a full-fledged subject of international relations. The country’s foreign policy is based on the principles of the sovereign equality of states, the non-use of force or the threat of force, the inviolability of borders, the territorial integrity of states, the peaceful settlement of disputes, non-interference in the internal affairs of other states and other universally recognized principles and norms of international law. The New Constitution of the country states: “The Republic of Uzbekistan pursues a peaceful foreign policy aimed at the all-round development of bilateral and multilateral relations with states and international organizations”[1].

In this regard, Uzbekistan occupies a leading place in Central Asia in expanding mutually beneficial cooperation with foreign countries. The presence in the market of trade, economic, investment, financial, as well as infrastructural relations with developing countries, such as Russia, China, the European Union, etc., The guidelines

for the development of bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and China are being updated [2]. The focus is on aspects of cooperation in the field of trade, investment, industrial cooperation, energy, transport, innovation, “green” and digital economy, programs in the fields of healthcare, education and culture [3].

For China, Uzbekistan is a state with a wide consumer market, cheap labor, a stable political environment and a positive system of public administration. The interests of the Celestial Empire are aimed at the business environment of Uzbekistan, huge opportunities for initiatives to form a productive development infrastructure.

METHODS

An analysis of the available data indicates that China has taken a strong leading position in foreign trade with Uzbekistan. In 2018, China’s share in foreign trade turnover amounted to 18.7%, which exceeded \$6.4 billion. The total volume of Chinese investments in 2018 was \$6.65 billion [3]. However, according to Chinese sources, China’s direct investment amounted to \$3.2 billion in 2019.

In 2021-2022, China’s investments amounted to about 17.9%. By the end of 2021, this figure amounted to \$9 billion [3]. Chinese investments in Uzbekistan are diversified and range from oil and gas to agriculture and logistics [4]. In particular, the Chinese conglomerate “Jinsheng Group” has made significant investments in a textile factory in Uzbekistan, which began operations in 2017. The annual output of cotton yarn is 22,000 metric tons, 95% of the factory’s output is exported, and half of the production is sold to China. “Xin Zhong Yuan Ceramics”, based in Foshan, launched a \$150 million ceramic production line in Uzbekistan in 2017 due to cheap ceramic raw materials, low energy costs, and a significant local consumer market. In March 2021, as part of a virtual meeting, the governments of Uzbekistan and China signed an agreement to attract large Chinese enterprises to Uzbekistan, and the government of Uzbekistan presented forty project concepts for consideration by Chinese investors. In 2017, a large loan from the China Development Bank in the amount of \$1.2 billion was issued to “Uzbekneftegaz” for the development of “Олтин Йўл”, a chemical liquid fuel from natural gas [5].

One of the important steps aimed at expanding economic ties and increasing the level of trade turnover was the introduction into practice of a regime of favorable mutual exchange of experience in this area. This made it possible to reach the mark of \$9 billion for the first time at the end of 2022, and in 7 months of 2023, China became the main trading partner of Uzbekistan with a total trade of \$6.9 billion, which represents an increase of 30.5% [6].

RESULTS

Within the framework of cooperation, Uzbekistan is open to diversifying its infrastructure network and expanding new export markets. At a meeting in Beijing,

within the framework of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, Uzbekistan presented the program “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” in Chinese, which confirms the improvement of economic relations between the state and China. One of the priorities for Uzbekistan is the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway, which provides Uzbekistan with access to the markets of South Asia. It should be noted that Uzbekistan has signed a five-year program of trade and investment cooperation with China [7].

One of the central places in the development of the two countries is given to the transport artery uniting the Central Asian region along the Silk Road. China’s investments in transport corridors are aimed at close integration with Uzbekistan, the creation of a reliable transit and transport route to Western countries.

The construction of the “Central Asia-China” pipeline is aimed at supplying the region with an important fuel and energy product. The Uzbek-Chinese agreements are aimed at filling this pipeline, including with Uzbek natural gas. According to experts from CNPC and “Uzbekneftegaz”, the cost of the 4th line of the Uzbek section of the “Central Asia-China” gas pipeline is \$800 million. It connects the existing infrastructure on the territory of Uzbekistan with the Tajik section of the “Central Asia-China” gas pipeline under construction [8].

In recent years, Uzbekistan has achieved tangible indicators in the country’s economic development. We are talking about foreign direct investment in the amount of \$25 billion, while about 59 thousand investment programs have been implemented and over 2.5 million new jobs have been created. The state has set itself ambitious goals of economic transformation. The government of Uzbekistan aims to achieve a GDP of \$100 billion, increase exports by more than \$30 billion, and attract 80% growth in the country’s GDP through the private sector. By 2030, Uzbekistan plans to join the World Trade Organization and become a state with an above-average per capita income [9].

DISCUSSION

According to leading experts, it should be noted that Uzbek-Chinese relations are aimed at mutually beneficial cooperation and development. This is confirmed by the “China-Central Asia” Summit, held on May 18-19, 2023 in the city of Xi’an. The last summit was devoted to economic cooperation with the post-Soviet republics. In the first four months of 2023 alone, China’s trade with five Central Asian countries increased by 37% compared to the same period in 2022 and amounted to more than \$25 billion. In general, at the end of 2022, the trade turnover with the summit participants exceeded \$70 billion.

Modern models for trade and investment cooperation, interaction towards high-quality development in the field of digital economy, e-commerce and innovative business projects are important for the two countries. Priority in cooperation are

“green” ideas on renewable energy sources, comprehensive support for industrial enterprises of both sides in the use of solar, wind and hydroelectric energy, encouraging the growth of new energy vehicles in the trade market of Uzbekistan, etc.

Back in 2013, an agreement on friendship and cooperation was signed between Uzbekistan and China. Article 12 outlines the necessary measures to develop exchanges and cooperation in the field of culture, education, health, tourism, sports and other areas of mutual interest, and strengthen friendly contacts between the media, scientific and educational institutions, and art groups [10]. In order to strengthen mutually beneficial relations, there is a commonality and similarity of the positions of the two states on regional and international issues, which are of great importance. Documents were signed on equipping the healthcare sector with modern medical equipment, as well as a Memorandum of Understanding in the field of veterinary medicine and plant inspection quarantine [11].

Over the past 6 years, progress has been made in the development of traditional, folk medicine, as well as remote technologies aimed at ensuring the well-being and health of the peoples of the two countries. During the pandemic, there was especially gratuitous bilateral assistance in overcoming the coronavirus infection. According to sources, during the epidemic that spread in China, the Uzbek government sent two batches of medical supplies to China without delay. When Uzbekistan found itself in critical conditions, China not only provided humanitarian aid, but also held several video conferences to exchange experience in the fight against coronavirus [12].

In addition, modern ambitious projects in the field of healthcare have been concluded. For example, the construction of a Chinese-Uzbek medical texnopark will confirm new heights of cooperation between Uzbekistan and China [13].

In the humanitarian spheres, including education, cooperation is on the rise. Cooperation in the field of active student exchange is vigorous, and the Confucius Institutes in Tashkent and Samarkand are training a number of language specialists for the two countries. A galaxy of sinologists has emerged, who are “ambassadors of Sino-Uzbek friendship” [14]. With their participation, a lot of work has begun on the translation and publication of literary sources, filmography, broadcasting of television programs (the information channel “UPandaCinema” is especially popular), interregional exchange of personnel for various fields of activity. In recent years, China has trained more than 6,500 specialists in various fields for Uzbekistan, who today contribute to the reform of modern Uzbekistan [14].

It is worth noting the expansion of cooperation between the countries within the framework of the “dialogue between civilizations”. Cultural ties have reached a new level. The State Academic Bolshoi Theater of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Nava’i and the Khorezm Regional Theater were honored to become members of the

International Theater League “Silk Road”. Both sides issued stamps “Sino-Uzbek Archaeology of the Silk Road”, in addition, a joint musical composition “Quyosh chiqar sharqdan mangu” dedicated to the 30th anniversary of the establishment of Uzbek-Chinese diplomatic relations was created.

Joint cultural projects, including art festivals, gala concerts, exhibitions, seminars, contribute to the strengthening and spiritual mutual enrichment of the two countries. More and more Chinese tourists are showing interest in the original history of Uzbekistan. In this regard, back in 2013, the launch of a project for the archaeological restoration of the ancient city of Khiva was announced. Now this project has already been successfully completed, which gave the ancient city of Khiva a new shine [14].

CONCLUSION

Thus, summarizing the above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1) Prospects for cooperation between Uzbekistan and China are aimed at the comprehensive development of trade, economic and investment relations. There is a dynamic growth of Chinese investments in the Uzbek market. Chinese investment in Uzbekistan is diversified and ranges from oil and gas to agriculture and logistics.

2) Priority is given to infrastructure projects to expand new export markets through the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway, which will ensure Uzbekistan’s access to the markets of South Asia.

3) Uzbekistan’s economic growth is achieved through foreign direct investment. This leads to an increase in the country’s GDP at the expense of the private sector, and in the future, the country’s accession to the World Trade Organization.

4) The point of growth has been achieved in the field of green and digital economy, representing the implementation of priority areas of bilateral cooperation between Uzbekistan and China. Modern projects advantageously represent advanced methods of renewable energy sources, comprehensive support for industrial enterprises of the two countries.

5) Ambitious projects in the field of healthcare play a key role in the development of Uzbek-Chinese relations. Especially within the framework of the effective use of traditional medicine among the population.

6) One of the important directions in the development of Uzbek-Chinese relations is the humanitarian sphere. The peoples of the two countries are becoming even closer thanks to the mutual exchange of experience in the field of education, science, culture and art.

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